

INCIDENCE OF SICKLE CELL ANEMIA AND ITS ASSOCIATED MANIFESTATIONS IN THE EASTERN TRIBAL POPULATION OF GUJARAT.

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Abstract

Introduction: This study investigated sickle cell disease (SCD) among the tribal population of Eastern Gujarat, India. The objectives were to determine the incidence, potential causes, healthcare models for diet, mortality index, and morbidity index of SCD.

Methodology: A retrospective hospital-based study was conducted on 600 tribal participants. Data was collected from medical records between June 1st, 2019, and June 27th, 2019. Ethical approval was obtained, and participant consent was acquired. Inclusion criteria included diagnosed SCD patients. Patients who had undergone surgery, females in their menstrual cycle, and non-SCD patients were excluded. Data was analysed using SPSS 16.0 software.

Results: The highest incidence of SCD was observed in the 10-20 year age group for males and the 21-30 year age group for females. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found between male and female patients in red blood cell (RBC) count, hemoglobin (Hb), white blood cell (WBC) count, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and packed cell volume (PCV).

Conclusion: SCD patients exhibited lower RBC count, Hb concentration, PCV, and RBC indices, but higher WBC counts. Significant gender differences were observed in p-values for several parameters. Due to limitations in data recording, commenting on mortality was difficult. The study suggests that malnutrition due to poverty is a concern and balanced diets are necessary to minimize SCD incidence and morbidity.

Key Words: Sickle Cell Disease, Tribal Population, Incidence, Morbidity, Gender Difference

INTRODUCTION:

In 1910, James Herrick cardiologist by profession 1st described sickle shaped cells in a dental student who presented with pain and symptoms of anemia. Herrick saw sickle shaped red blood cell under microscope and coined the term “sickle-shaped” due to its appearance. ⁽¹⁾ In 1927, Hahn and Gillespie suggested RBC sickling by demonstrating that shape changes could be done by saturating cell suspension with carbon dioxide.⁽²⁾ In the late 1940’s and early 1950’s the nature of the disease become more clearer. Linus Pauling and his colleague Dr. Harvey Itano in 1945 discovered that hemoglobin had a different structure. ⁽³⁾ Then it was confirmed by demonstration of the differential migration of sickle versus normal hemoglobin by gel electrophoresis.⁽⁴⁾ Vernon Ingram demonstrated that the mutant sickle hemoglobin (Hb S) differed from normal hemoglobin A by a single amino acid.⁽⁵⁾

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is the most common genetic disorder and is most commonly inherited disorder with potentially serious complication. The incidence of severe complications is high not only because of biological aspects inherent to sickle cell disease, but also because the disease is poorly understood by healthcare staff i.e. lacks of visibility. ⁽⁶⁾ The sickle cell mutation affects the beta globin gene of adult hemoglobin causing substitution of glutamic amino acid for valine at 6th position which changes the behavior to sickle cell hemoglobin. ⁽⁷⁾

Estimates suggest that nearly 30 million individuals are affected worldwide and represent major health concern because of its associated significant mortality. ⁽⁸⁾ Sickle cell anemia is particularly common among people whose ancestors come from sub Saharan Africa, India, Saudi Arabia and Mediterranean countries. Approximately 90,000 births in Nigeria, 40,000 in Democratic Republic of Congo, 40,000 children born in India while 10,000 in America and 10,000 in The Eastern Mediterranean and 2000 in Europe. ⁽⁹⁾

Fig 1. Incidence of Newborns with Sickle Cell Anemia worldwide

Fig 1. Shows the incidence of Newborns with sickle cell anemia. ⁽¹⁰⁾

According to the 2011 Census, the tribal population of India is 8.6 %, which is about 67.8 million people. ⁽¹¹⁾ It demonstrates the highest incidence in India and Africa (fig 1). In Gujarat, total incidence of sickle cell trait was 11.37%. ⁽¹²⁾ Madhya Pradesh has the peak burden of 9, 61,492 sickle heterozygotes and 67,861 sickle homozygotes. Further, 27 of the 45 districts in Madhya Pradesh come under the sickle cell belt and the incidence of HbS differs from 10 to 33%. ⁽¹³⁾ In Maharashtra, the incidence of sickle cell trait in different tribes differs from 0 to 35%. ⁽¹⁴⁾ In Kerala, a very high incidence of HbS is seen which ranges from 18.2 to 34.1 %. ⁽¹⁵⁾

Fig 2. Incidence of Sickle Cell trait in India

The overall incidence of Sickle cell trait in various states of India is shown in Fig 2. Figure shows the highest incidence observed in Madhya Pradesh followed by Gujarat, Maharashtra, Kerala, Tamil Nadu and Assam⁽¹⁶⁾.

This study will help to upgrade the knowledge regarding sickle cell disease. It is also supportive information for genetic counseling and outcome of this study may help to government health care agencies to make policy decision to monitor the life threatening disease.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Study conducted by Saxena D., et al., on Situational analysis of sickle cell disease in Gujarat,⁽¹⁷⁾ India in 2017 holds that SCD is a major public health distress in tribal population in Gujarat. It has 89.12 lacs tribal populations and has approximately 9,00,000 sickle cell trait and 70,000 SCD patients. This study shows prevalence of 0.6%–35% conducted among medical students, tribal children, and tribal adolescents, with several screening methods such as DTT/HPLC methods were used to estimate the prevalence, alluding the need for standardization. It was also found that not only tribal

population, but also nontribal population have the threat of receiving SCD that needs to be further investigated properly. Qualitative studies with SCD patients are required to understand the quality of life and morbidity pattern.

In 2010 a study conducted by H.I. Hyacinth et al., shows the role of protein/energy malnutrition in HbSS. It shows the direct measurements leading to the impression of a relative shortage of nutrients for growth and development, even though there are adequate dietary resources. Although there is data supportive of the usefulness of macronutrient supplementation, still recommended dietary allowances (RDAs) for the general population are not enough for the sickle cell patient. Micronutrient deficiencies, which includes outcomes of vitamin D deficiency associated with incomplete ossification.⁽¹⁸⁾

In 2016 a study through by Gayatri Desai et al., observed that total of 164 patients diagnosed with SCD out of which 72 patients (43.9%) had SCD pain crises, 59 (35.9%) were hospitalized, 43 (26.2%) had history of blood transfusions and 3 (1.8%) died in the course of follow-up. Compared to baseline, coverage of pneumococcal vaccine (0.6% to 78.5%, $p < 0.001$) and hydroxyurea (4.5% to 50.0%) were significantly improved. It was observed that marked decrease in the proportion of patients with ≥ 3 pain crises per year (35.4% to 9.8%) and the proportion of patients with ≥ 1 hospitalization per year (56.7% to 36.0%) with no noteworthy variation in patients with ≥ 1 blood transfusion in the last year (32.9% to 26.2%).⁽¹⁹⁾

In 2013 a study conducted by Sophie Lanzkron, et al., reported 16,654 sickle cell-related deaths. Mean age at death was very much different for males (33.4 years) than for females (36.9 years). In a regression model controlling for gender, the mean age at death increased by 0.36 years for each year of the study. The median age at death in 2005 was 42 years for females and 38 years for males. The overall mortality rate increased (0.7%) each year during the period of study. The adult (>19 years of age) mortality rate increased by 1% each year during the period of study. The pediatric mortality rate decreased by 3% each year during the period of study.⁽²⁰⁾

In 2015 Roshan B Colah et al., reviewed SCD in tribal populations in India stated the fact

that the sickle gene is highly predominant with number of heterozygote individual changing from 1-40 per cent. Co-inheritance of the sickle gene has been observed with β -thalassemia, HbD Punjab and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency. Most of the screening programs in India now use high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) test even though the solubility test is also sensitive and relative cheaper. SCD among tribal population is alarming with fewer incidences of painful crises, infections, acute chest syndrome and need hospitalization than the nontribal groups due to various reasons. It is also reported that very high incidence of α -thalassemia among these as well as higher fetal hemoglobin levels. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Another study in 2016 carried out by Yadav R et al., explained that Splenomegaly was the most common clinical manifestation observed (71.4%), overall, 63.5% patients had a history of blood transfusion. The signs and symptoms recorded in their study were icterus, joint pain, pallor, fever, and fatigue. Majority of the patients showed onset of disease preceding 3 years (SCA 44.3% and SBT 35.9%). Mean haemoglobin levels among SCA individuals were higher than SBT patients. While, mean fetal hemoglobin levels among SBT individuals in their study presented the contrary trend. ⁽²¹⁾

In 2018 a study conducted by Snehamayee Nayak et al., consists of total 68 clinical events in 60 patients during the period of study in which more than 50% of them falls in 0-5 years age group. Mean age for diagnosis was found to be 2.79 years. Severe anemia with blood transfusion was the most common cause of hospitalization trailed by painful crises. Mean Hb level in the children was found to be 6.65(\pm 2.38). More than one third of children had accompanying nutritional anemia. Children with high HbF level were found to have less episodes of painful crises. ⁽²²⁾

A study conducted in 2019 by Mombo LE1 et al., found that Homozygous SCA patients had low erythrocyte values (red blood cells: $2.50 \times 10^{12}/L$, haemoglobin: 7.20 g/dL and haematocrit: 20.70%) and raised leucocyte values (WBC: $14.40 \times 10^9/L$, lymphocytes: $5.24 \times 10^9/L$ and monocytes: $1.60 \times 10^9/L$). Most of the SCA patients diagnosed severe anaemia (67%), normochromia (76%), lymphocytosis (73%) and monocytosis (84%). A Hb level of < 8.5 g/dL together with a WBC's level above 9.5×10^9 cells/L was used as screening tool to detect homozygous SCA patients, with sensitivity of 84.4% and specificity of 97.8%. ⁽²³⁾

AIMS and OBJECTIVES:

- To study incidence of sickle cell disease among the tribal population of EasternGujarat.
- To evaluate potential causes of the disease.
- To develop holistic models of health care in terms of diet.
- To find mortality index of SCD in tribal population.
- To find morbidity index of SCD in tribal population.

METHODOLOGY:

- **Study Procedure:** This is a hospital based, retrospective study of tribal population of eastern Gujarat. This study will be based on the factual data records obtained from a tertiary health care while maintaining the confidentiality of the patient's data as and where required.
- **Sample size:** 600 subjects were analyzed for the incidence of sickle cell and its manifestations in a tertiary health care.
- **Data Collection:** The data was collected from medical record of tertiary health care in Eastern Gujarat from 1st June 2019 to 27th June 2019.
- **Ethical consideration institutional:** Ethics committee's approval will be taken prior to the study. The consent from the participant will be taken before the study.
- **Inclusion Criteria:** All sickle cell diagnosed patients in a tertiary health care.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Non sickle cell patients and patients who have undergone surgery and female subjects in menstrual cycle.
- **Statistical Analysis:** The data collected into Excel sheet were entered into SPSS 16.0 version. Frequency tables were generated. t-test was used to compare means differences between males and females. Statistical significance was considered at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Fig 3. Demographic Data

Fig 1 showed that 74.79% of the patients recorded have been living in the rural region, 10.5% in urban region and 14.71% in semi urban region. The percentage of patient recorded in Non matric, matric intermediate, and graduate are 46.07%, 31.38%, 11.01% and 11.51% respectively.

Fig 4. Incidence of Male-Female sickle cell positive-negative data

The overall incidence of SCD is shown in Fig 2 in male and female. Data showed that highest incidence observed between age group 10-20 years in male and 21-30 in female group, which contradicts earlier observation and resemblance in children.

Fig 5. 2-tailed male female ratio of sickle cell positive

This was observed from fig 3 that p-value (2-tailed) of RBC count, Hb, WBC, MCV, MCH and PCV are significant between male and female population. ⁽²⁴⁾

Fig 6. Mean value of various parameters of hemogram

1. There has been no significant difference found between mean RBC count for sickle cell positive male and female while there is a slight difference found in mean Hb between male and female. Mean Hb is slightly greater in females than males. There has been marked difference observed in mean WBC, it is greater in females than in males. This might be due to females being more prone to certain infections for various reasons, including biological differences, social indifferences, and restrictive cultural norms. ⁽²⁵⁾ MCV and MCH value were found greater in male than female while there was no difference found for RDW and PCV between males and females.

DISCUSSION:

The p-value was found higher in males (0.997) for RBC count compared to females (0.366) having sickle cell anemia. The mean value for RBC count of sickle cell positive male is 4.8106 and of female it is 4.7259. The mean RBC count found in these study is higher than the study conducted in Ghana in 2018 by Charles Antwi-Boasiako et al., ⁽²⁴⁾ However, p-value for mean hemoglobin was higher in females (0.439) as compared to males (0.221) in sickle cell anemia. The mean value for Hb Concentration of sickle cell positive male is 10.5651 and for female it is 9.9095. Total Hb is low in all SCA subjects, it may be due to active hemolysis. Though Hb concentration is lower than the normal ranges, the average Hb is higher than the study conducted by Nagose. ⁽²⁶⁾

There was significant difference between females (p-value 0.039) and males (p-value 0.739) of WBC. The mean value of WBC Count for sickle cell positive male is $99.50 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$ and for female it is $117.98 \times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$. The results found in this study contradicts with research conducted by Antwi-Boasiako in 2018⁽²⁴⁾ while found similar to the study conducted by Nagose.⁽²⁶⁾

In case of MCV, p-values were found to be significant in both the genders in males (0.01) and females (0.049) respectively. The mean value for MCV of sickle cell positive male is 69.683 and for female it is 67.54. Usually MCV is greater in SCD patients due to the increasing need of erythropoiesis and chronic hemolysis which leads macrocytosis. It may be related to a folic acid deficiency. Low MCV in this study is observed as compared to the above mentioned study may be due to co-existing iron deficiency anemia and other unknown factors such as α -thalassemia which is frequent and often associated to SCD.⁽²⁷⁻²⁹⁾ Thus iron and folic acid supplements are necessary to minimize co-morbidities.

P-values were found to be insignificant for MCH in both males (0.179) and females (0.717) respectively. The mean value for MCH of sickle cell positive male is 22.5111 and for female it is 21.1547. Even it was insignificant for RDW in both the genders. It is lesser in males (0.164) than the females (0.493) while the mean value for RDW of sickle cell positive male is 18.3063 and for female it is 18.9368. RDW and MCH are more or less similar to other works.⁽²⁶⁾

The p-values were found significant in males for PCV while was found insignificant in females for the same parameter. It was 0.07 and 0.32 in males and females respectively. The mean value for PCV of sickle cell positive male is 32.9764 and for female it is 32.0638. It is found higher than the study conducted by Kohchale SR in 2015. This may be due to the lower sample size of Kohchale SR.⁽³⁰⁾

Majority of the published studies focused on screening knowledge, attitudes and practices or hematological profile of SCD patients. The incidence varies from 0.6% to 35% for sickle cell. However there is no standardization implemented as different methodologies with different approaches and diverse grouping of castes and target population were included. Even there is not any uniformity in the screening test used and also its validity.⁽¹⁷⁾

CONCLUSION:

Sickle cell Anemia patients have lower values for RBC count, Hb Concentration, PCV and RBC Indices but have greater values of WBCs. There has been marked difference found between male and female p-value for RBC count. The p-value was found higher in males for RBC Count compared to females having sickle cell anemia. However, p-value for mean hemoglobin was higher in females as compared to males in sickle cell anemia. It was also observed that p-value in WBC for female is higher than males. The p-value for MCV, MCH, RDW and PCV observed was greater in females than males. Only one case of blood transfusion history was reported in this study. It difficult to comment on blood transfusion in the patients of sickle cell positive cases associated with other co- morbidities. It was observed that due to low poverty in tribes of Gujarat, there is more incidence of malnutrition and lack of essential elements for normal growth. It is necessary to provide balanced diet to minimize incidence and morbidities in SCD. Considering limitations/ lacunas in documenting of records, it is difficult to comment on mortality.

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